

Time and Quantum Bound States (Part 2)

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The Heisenberg uncertainty principles $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$ and $\Delta E \Delta t \geq \hbar/2$ appear to display a certain symmetry between (p, x) and (E, t) , however, no time operator exists, while operators for p, x and E do. Furthermore, there are questions as to what time t represents as quantum mechanics is a statistical theory. For a bound state, time enters through $\exp(-iEt)$ the time dependent portion of the wavefunction. In addition, if one thinks of a quantum single particle state in terms of an ensemble, this same time may represent the evolution of the ensemble. The ensemble, however, is a mathematical construct related to an average picture in this case. In this note, we try to investigate these issues.

Free Single Particle

In quantum mechanics, a free single particle has a wavefunction of $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ where $E = p^2/2m$. It seems in this case, one tries to link x and t as there exists an expression for a phase velocity i.e. E/p which is not $v = p/m$. (Group velocity for a wavepacket is introduced to create a classical analogue.) To see further that x and t are considered to be linked consider a calculation of the Bohm-Aharonov effect (1). A potential $N(x)$ exists in space, but yields no force, so p does not change. As a charged particle moves through a region with $N(x)$ $\exp(ipx)$ is unaffected, but a phase enters through $\exp(-i \int_{t_1}^{t_2} N(x(t)) dt)$. The term $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to a physical wavelength and $\exp(ip^2/2m t)$ to a frequency which is less readily observable. If x and t are linked and x is related to a physical oscillation (wavelength) in space, then t should be related to a physical oscillation in time. The wavelength and frequency are in addition related to resolution of space and time. This leads to the question of a single particle bound state, where $\exp(ipx)$ appears, but one does not follow the physical stochastic motion of a particle in time nor is $\exp(ipx)$ associated with a physical path in time.

Bound Single Particle

A free single particle is described by $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ ($E = p^2/2m$) with x and t being linked. A bound single particle, however, is described in a statistical manner, like a single particle in a classical gas. One does not follow a single particle in time in classical gas, rather average values of particles in the gas such as temperature, pressure etc are measured in time. For equilibrium, they are usually static.

It seems quantum mechanics attempts to describe a single particle in terms of a classical statistical ensemble i.e. with free particles which frequently change their momenta due to collisions. In classical statistical mechanics, collisions are due to two-body scattering, but in quantum mechanics they occur from stochastic potential hits. Thus, one cannot separate an energy equation from statistical collisions in the quantum case. In such a case, one would expect a single particle may appear at any x position just as a free particle $\exp(ipx)$. Time is removed because one has equilibrium. One expects the probability for a particle p at x is $\exp(i$

$g(p,x)$) where $g(p,x)$ is not separable. If the probability were real, it would have to decrease or increase with x because it must be a function of x as average kinetic energy changes with x . $\exp(i g(p,x))$ is a function of x , yet has modulus 1 everywhere giving the sense that the particle can be anywhere. An imaginary probability here is, however, related to periodicity which is a major issue to be considered. (We discuss this in the next section.) Due to arguments we have considered in other notes, we take $\exp(i g(p,x)) = \exp(ipx)$.

This probability is established by measuring the particle with momentum p many different times at x , thus many time values enter in establishing a weight of $a(p)$. For example, if one tried to use $\exp(-ipp/2m t)$ one would have: $a(p) [\exp(-i pp/2m (t_1+t_2+t_3+....))]$ where t_i are arbitrary times. For the equilibrium case, it has been argued one need not consider time.

Quantum mechanics has the extra constraint, unlike classical statistical mechanics, at each x :

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \ a(p)\exp(ipx)] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

The first term on the LHS of ((1)) is an average of free particle kinetic energies with a normalization factor of $W(x)$ the wavefunction. It should be remembered, however, that different p values would not exist at x if it were not for the potential $V(x)$ which delivers stochastic hits. Momentum p is not a function of time because one does not follow the particle in time. Rather, average kinetic energy changes from x to $x+dx$ strictly through a phase change in the p probabilities and a shift in $W(x+dx)$. Thus, acceleration is due in a sense to interference, although this is purely a statistical consideration because the data for x is collected over many time instances so there is no physical interference. Furthermore, the interference does not have to be a "canceling" of "anything", it may be due to some cases of the particle entering a dx region combined with cases where the particle reverses direction i.e. leaves the dx region.

If one considers a particle in a box with infinite potentials at the wall, the wavefunction is: $1/(2i) [\exp(i p a x) - \exp(-i p a x)]$. At first, one might suggest that $\exp(i p a x)$ represents a physically forward moving wave, but it is a statistical average of many $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ terms. Thus, a trajectory based on $\exp(i p a x)$ is a statistical construction. In this case, $\exp(i p a x)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ are linked, but this only describes average ensemble behaviour.

It may also be noted that in a single particle system, the quantum particle may be at x at many different time values e.g. it may be at x at t_1 , move forward due to stochastic hits, move backward back to x at t_5 etc. A single time t_i , however, may only be associated with one x value in a single system. Thus, x and t seem to be on very different footings even though in general x and ct are both considered dimensions.

Complex Probability

In classical physics, probability is real and sums to 1, such as the probability for a coin to land with heads or tails or a die to land with one of each of the 6 possible choices. How is it possible to have a complex conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ when p is a clearly defined

outcome? Consider the case of p and $-p$ for $a(p) = a(-p)$ with a similar result holding for $a(p) = -a(-p)$. Then:

$$P(p/x) + P(-p/x) = 2 \cos(px) \quad a(p) = a(-p) \quad ((2))$$

In such a case, probability is real, not complex, but there are two distinct outcomes. We argue that physically a particle is in an oscillatory resonance in an “average picture”. For some x values, it moves forward and for others it moves backwards etc. Thus, one measures probability based on the position x i.e. a conditional probability. Such a conditional situation does not exist in a coin or die toss. Thus, one is not really dealing with independent probabilities to have a particular p or $-p$ at each point x .

How is it possible for a particle to move backwards and forwards in different x regions? Furthermore, how is it possible for its probability to diminish near zeroes of $\cos(px)$? We argue that a potential $V(x)$ may be written in a stochastic manner as $\sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. If $V(k) = V(-k)$ this potential has the same $\cos(kx)$ appearance. Thus, the $\pm k$ hits that are given are periodic in space and it is possible to have a k -momentum particle moving forward or backwards in different k regions.

If a particle moves backwards while others are moving forwards, it is as if energy is lost i.e. $p^2/2m \cos(px)/W(x)$ for $\cos(px) < 0$. Thus, at a given x , some p values actually remove kinetic energy from the average: $\sum_p p^2/2m P(p/x)$. It should be pointed out, however, that these are all average calculations taken over many different time points or over many systems in an ensemble at the same time. Thus, it seems time is ignored completely. One tends to think of an average scenario as an actual physical system which it is not. The physical system it seems is one with much stochastic motion in which it is difficult to see patterns. Patterns emerge by presenting a statistical picture as in classical statistical mechanics.

Quantum mechanics seems to provide a statistical description of a bound state with a complex probability $P(p/x)$ such that the modulus $\exp(ipx)$ is identical for all x and yet includes the variable x so there may be different average $f(p)$ values (e.g. $f(p) = p^2/2m$) at different x . This results in unusual backwards-forwards motion as a function of x , yet this is statistical as $\cos(px)$ is obtained by taking measurements at each x which occur at a whole range of time values. Unlike classical physics, the particle is not at x at t_1 and $x+dx$ at t_1+dt_1 .

Different Times in the Quantum Bound System

As a result, it seems to be confusing to consider time in a quantum system as there are different candidates. First, one may consider an actual particle moving stochastically in time. At t_1 it is at x_1 with p_1 , then it receives a large hit and moves to x_5 with p_5 at t_2 etc, then it may move backwards. This path is complicated and is replaced with a statistical approach just as in classical statistical mechanics. The statistical approach based on conditional probabilities, however, still accounts for the different allowable p values of a particle and describes their probabilities at x i.e. $P(p/x)$. One may calculate: $\sum_p p P(p/x)$ and $\sum_p p^2/2m P(p/x)$ yielding two velocity values $\langle p \rangle/m$ and v_{rms} which are usually different. One may construct two “statistical” paths linking x to t , but as this is only a statistical calculation, it does not represent any real motion, although v_{rms} mimics classical physical motion.

For a single particle, we argued in the first section that there exists a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ with x and t linked. Given the statistical approach used to describe average behaviour of single particle bound system (i.e. $P(p/x)$), there seems to be no way to link x and t for a single particle, thus $\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ which does seem to measure a physical frequency associated with a single particle state does not come into play even though $\exp(ipx)$ appears in $P(p/x)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is simply a probability at x , it does not describe any kind of motion through x in time. Such a path is only a statistical conjecture because physically observed values such as KE average at x depend on interference of $p^2/2m P(p/x)$ terms and stochastic potential hits occur even though $\exp(ipx)$ describes a free particle.

If $\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ describes a physical frequency of a particle, is there an equivalent for a bound system? If one considers the Schrodinger time-independent equation with $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ written as Fourier series and collects $\exp(ipx)$ terms:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \text{Sum over } k \ V(k)a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) holds at all x and officially does not contain time. It shows $V(k)$ interacting with various $a(p-k)$ to form $a(p)$, where $V(k)$ is the k Fourier transform of $V(x)$. The term $a(p)$ is obtained from measurements at many different times. Nevertheless, there appears to be a physical cycling represented by ((3)) which suggests $a(p,t) = \exp(-iEt) a(p)$. In other words, the Hamiltonian H on the LHS of ((3)) acts as a time evolution operator. In such a case, time is associated with the evolution of the ensemble system. $\exp(-iEt)$ suggests periodic time motion as opposed to no time behaviour, but is not readily measured. It disappears from density $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ and there is no negative energy present to allow for the formation of a $\cos(Et)$ type term as in the $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ case.

As a consequence, p represents a specific momentum value which a single particle may take whereas E represents average energy a particle has at each x point. " X " represents a specific point in space where a particle may be found whereas t time like average energy applies to an ensemble. In that sense, the two variables set (p,x) and (E,t) are very different and it is easy to become confused about time in quantum mechanics which it seems should be used to describe the evolution of an average system. $W(x)$, the wavefunction is already an ensemble value i.e. $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ of relative conditional probabilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for a free single particle $\exp(ipx)\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ where it is assumed that x is linked to t through a phase velocity. A bound state is described as an ensemble of free states i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but the time dependence of W is $\exp(-iEt)$ where E is the average energy suggesting frequency is no longer due to $\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ or some kind of averaging of $\exp(i p^2/2m t)$ terms, but rather is a cycling among different so-called free states $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $a(p) p^2/2m + \text{Sum over } k \ V(k)a(p-k) = E$ where $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \exp(ikx)$. It may be noted that at each x , $\exp(-iEt) = \exp(-i (\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) p^2/2m + V(x)) t)$.

The bound state system is described in terms of $\exp(ipx)$ values, but these are associated with many different time measurements, just as in the classical statistical mechanical case. We

argue that t in quantum mechanics is a time associated with the ensemble $W(x)$ and E is an average energy which holds at each x . Thus, p and x and E and t seem to be on very different footings. (Similar ideas have been discussed in previous notes .)

References

1. Saldana, P. Local Description of the Bohm-Aharonov Effect with Quantum Mechanic Field (2020) <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.10650>